

Table 2. Effect of *T. viride* alone and with cytozyme on ShB infection. Assam, India, 1983.

Treatment	Sheaths infected (%)
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> alone	74.6
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> + <i>T. viride</i>	60.3
Inoculation with <i>R. solani</i> + <i>T. viride</i> with 2 h cytozyme dip	90.0
LSD (0.05)	14.5
CV (%)	12.1

The root dip was prepared by mixing 2 ml cytozyme with 24 ml water. Seedling roots were dipped for 5 min and 2 h the first year and for 2 h the second year, then air-dried for 2 h. Rice variety Pusa 2-21 was transplanted 18 Aug 1982, 25 d after seeding (DAS), at 4 seedlings/pot in inoculated soil (inoculum in maize-meal sand medium added at 5% of soil). Mahsuri was transplanted on 2 Aug 1983, 25 DAS.

Although cytozyme reduced ShB infection 1.5 mo after inoculation, the difference disappeared at 2.5 mo (Table 1). ShB suppression was more pronounced with *T. viride* than with cytozyme. However, the effect of *T. viride* was not pronounced on Mahsuri in 1983 (Table 2). When *T. viride* was used with cytozyme, its suppressing effect was nullified. □

Host plants of rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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We inoculated seedlings of 4 *Oryza* spp. and 18 weed species by confining separately in cages for 1 d with 20 brown planthoppers *Nilaparvata lugens* that had fed on plants infected with GSV strain 2. Inoculated plants were indexed by ELISA 1 mo later. Extracts of plants with absorbance at 405 nm higher than 3 times that of uninoculated plant extracts were considered to contain the virus.

All rices and five weed species were infected (see table). The infected rices showed typical GSV symptoms. None of the infected weeds showed clear

Absorbance at 405 nm in ELISA of extracts of plants infected with GSV after inoculation by GSV-viruliferous BPH. IRRI.

Species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants (no.)	Absorbance at 405 nm	
			Infected plants	Uninoculated plants (mean)
<i>Oryza australiensis</i>				
Acc. 100882	14	6	0.08–1.40	0.00
Acc. 101144	9	3	0.16–0.32	0.00
Acc. 101397	5	3	0.19–0.99	0.00
<i>O. barthii</i>	3	2	0.68–1.14	0.04
<i>O. latifolia</i>	10	4	0.27–0.70	0.03
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	3	3	0.09–0.33	0.00
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	10	4	0.05–0.14	0.01
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	9	5	0.24–0.96	0.05
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	10	2	0.08–0.40	0.02
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	10	2	0.07–0.13	0.02
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	10	1	0.10	0.03

symptoms. Weeds not infected with GSV were *Axonopus compressus*, *Brachiaria distachya*, *B. mutica*, *Chloris barbata*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Eleusine*

indica, *Eragrostis tenella*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Paspalidium flavidum*, and *Paspalum conjugatum*. □

Fungicides to control rice sheath blight (ShB)

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It has been difficult to find a good source of resistance to rice ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. We tested seven chemicals during transplanted aman season (Jul–Nov) 1987 on the BRRI farm. The experiment was set up in 3- × 2-m plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications.

Susceptible variety BR11 was transplanted at 30 d after seeding (DAS)

Effect of fungicides on ShB and rice yield.^a BRRI, T. aman, 1987.

Treatment	Disease index	Yield at 14% moisture (t/ha)
Fungicide		
Thiabendazole	3.5 abc	4.1 a
Iprodione	3.8 abc	3.9 ab
Thiabendazole + maneb	5.5 a	3.7 b
Propiconazole	2.0 cd	4.2 a
Thiophanate-methyl	2.7 bc	3.4 c
Thiophanatemethyl + thiram	3.2 bc	3.9 ab
Edifenphos	4.8 ab	4.1 a
Control (inoculation, no spray)	5.7 a	3.4 c
CV (%)	15.6	7.5

^aMeans of 3 replications. In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level (DMRT).

with 20- × 15-cm spacing. Recommended 60-40-40 kg NPK/ha was applied, using urea, triple

superphosphate, and muriate of potash. N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 21 d after transplanting (DT) and before